

A Survey of Decomposition Multi-Objective Optimization: PART I—Past and Future

Anonymous authors

Fig. A1. An illustrative example of weight vector generation in the 3-dimensional space by using the Das and Dennis’s method [1].

APPENDIX A TABLES

This section gives the tables complementary to our manuscript. Tables A1 to ?? summarize the selected works for different algorithmic components in MOEA/D.

TABLE A1
SELECTED WORKS FOR WEIGHT VECTOR SETTINGS IN MOEA/D.

SUBCATEGORY	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
Fixed methods	MOGLS [2]–[4], MOEA/D-RW [5]	Random method
	NSGA-III [6], MOEA/DD [7]	Multi-layer method
	UMOEA/D [8], [9], UMODE/D [10]	Uniform design
	Riesz s -energy function [11], RMA [12]	Others
Model-based adaptation methods	T-MOEAD [13], $pa\lambda$ -MOEA/D [14], apa -MOEA/D [15], DMOEA/D [16]	Polynomial model
	MOEA/D-LTD [17], [18], MOEA/D-GLCM [19]	Parametric model
	MOEA/D-SOM [20], MOEA/D-GNG [21], [22], CMoEA/RPA [23]	Neural networks
Delete-and-add	MOEA/D-AWA [24], MOEA/D-URAW [25], [26], AdaW [27]	Less crowded or promising areas
	CLIA [28], MOEA/D-AM2M [29], [30]	
	RVEA* [31], [32], iRVEA [33], OD-RVEA [34], EARPEA [35], g-DBEA [36]	Away from the promising areas
	A-NSGA-III [37], A ² -NSGA-III [38], AMOEAD [39], MOEA/D-TPN [40],	Regulated neighborhood
	TPEA-PBA [41], MaMOEA/D-2ADV [42], EMOSA [43], [44], AWA [45]	
	AWA-SSCWA [46], MOEA/D-HD [47]	
	AWD-MOEAD [48], FV-MOEAD [49], AR-MOEAD [50], MOEA-ABD [51]	Local niches of non-dominated solutions
E-IM-MOEAD [52], MOEA/D-AWVAM [53]		

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TABLE A2
SELECTED WORKS FOR SUBPROBLEM FORMULATIONS IN MOEA/D.

SUBPROBLEM FORMULATION	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
TCH variants	AASF [54], MOEA/AD [55]	Adapt the weighted metric parameter
	MOEA/D- <i>par</i> [56], MOEA/D-PaS [57], MSF and PSF [58]	
PBI variants	NSGA-III-AASF and NSGA-III-EPBI [59], MOEA/D-PaP [60]	Adapt the penalty parameter
	MOEA/D-APS and MOEA/D-SPS [61]	Inverted PBI method
	MOEA/D-IPBI [62], [63]	
	MOEA/D-LTD [18]	Augmented multiple distance metrics
Constrained Decomposition	MOEA/D-ACD [64], MOEA/D-LWS [65]	Reduce the improvement region
	MOEA/D-M2M [66], [67], MOEA/D-AM2M [30]	

TABLE A3
SELECTED WORKS FOR SELECTION MECHANISMS IN MOEA/D.

SELECTION MECHANISM	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
Mating selection	MOEA/D-DE [68], MOEA/D-TPN [69], MOEA/D-MRS [70]	Neighborhood versus global
	ENS-MOEA/D [71], MOEA/D-ATO [72]	Ensemble neighborhood
	MO-RCGA [73], SRMMEA [74], MOEA/D-EAM [75]	Neighborhood of solutions
Environmental selection	MOEA/D-DE [68], EFR [76]	Neighborhood versus global
	MOEA/DD [7], ISC-MOEA/D [77], g-DBEA [36], DDEA and DDEA+NS [36]	Prioritizing isolated regions
	VaEA [78], OLS [79], ASEA [80]	
	MOEA/D-STM [81], AOOSTM and AMOSTM [82], MOEA/D-IR [83]	Matching solutions and subproblems
	MOEA/D-ARS [84], MOEA/D-CD and MOEA/D-ACD [64], MOEA/D-GR [64], [85]	Global replacement
θ -DEA [86], MOEA/D-DU and EFR-RR [87], MOEA/D-CSM [88]	Local niche competition	

TABLE A4
SELECTED WORKS FOR REPRODUCTION OPERATORS IN MOEA/D.

REPRODUCTION OPERATOR	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
Swarm intelligence	dMOPSO [89], SDMOPSO [90], MOPSO/D [91], D ² MOPSO [92] MMOPSO [93], DEMPSO [94], MS-GPSO/D ^w [95], MaPSO [96]	PSO
	MOEA/D-ACO [97], ACO-Index [98], NMOACO/D [99], MACO/D-LOA [100]	ACO
	dMOABC [101], MOCS/D [102], MOGWO [103], MIWOALS [104]	Other SI
Model-based methods	MEDA/D [105], [106]	EDAs
	MOEA/D-GM [107]	Probabilistic graphic model
	MOEA/D-PBIL [108]	PBIL
	MACE-gD [109]	Cross-entropy method
	MOEA/D-CMA+I [110], MO-CMA-D [110], MOEA/D-CMA [111]	CMA-ES
	MOPC/D [112]	Probability collectives
	MOEA/D-LM [113], LGSEA [114]	Pareto set model
AOS and HH	MOEA/D-FRRMAB [115], MOEA/D-UCB-Tuned and MOEA/D-UCB-V [116] NSGA-III _{AP} and NSGA-III _{PM} [117], SaMOEA/D [118], MOEA/D-DYTS [119]	Adaptive operator selection
	MPADE [120], MOEA/D-CDE [121], AMOEA/D [122]	Parameter control
	MOEA/D-GHDE [123], EF-PD [124], MOEA/D-IMA [125]	Ensemble of operators
	MAB-HH [126], MOEA/D-HH _{sw} [127], MOEA/D-HH [128], MOEA/D-DRA-UCB [129] BoostMOEA/D-DRA [130], MOEA/D-LinUCB [131], MAB-based HH [132]	Hyper-heuristics
Mathematical programming	MOEA/D-LS [133], MOEA/D-RBF [134], MONSS [135], NSS-MO [136]	Direct search method
	MOEA/D-QS [137], MOEA/D-NMS [138]	KKTPM
	NSGA-III-KKTPM [139]–[141]	
Memetic search	MOMAD [142], PPLS/D [143]	Pareto local search
	CoMOLS/D [144], MONSD [145], MOMNS/D and MOMNS/V [146], LS/D [147] MOEA/D-TS [148], MOEA-MA [149], DMTS [150], MOEA/D-GLS [151]	Neighborhood search
	EMOSA [43], [44], MOMA-SA [152], EOMO [153]	Simulated annealing
	MOEA/D-GRASP [154], HEMH [155]	
	MOEA/D-MA [156], MOEA/D-BA [157]	Other local search operators

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TABLE A5
SELECTED WORKS FOR CONSTRAINT HANDLING IN MOEA/D.

SUBCATEGORY	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
Feasibility-driven method	CMOEA/D-DE-ATP [158], [159], g-DBEA [160], [161]	Constraint violation
	C-MOEA/D and C-NSGA-III [37], C-MOEA/DD [7]	Prioritize isolated regions
	MOEA/D-IEpsilon [162], ϵ -MOEA/D- δ [163], MOEA/D-WEO- ϵ CHT [164]	ϵ -constraint
Weight vector adaptation	RVEA [31], g-DEBA [36], CM2M [165]	Weight vector adaptation
Trade-off among convergence, diversity and feasibility	C-TAEA [166], MOEA/D-TW [167], IDW-M2M-CDP [?]	Multi-population
	PPS-MOEA/D [168], PPS-M2M [169], DC-NSGA-III [170]	Push and pull

TABLE A6
SELECTED WORKS FOR SURROGATE-ASSISTED MOEA/D FOR EXPENSIVE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS.

SUBCATEGORY	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
Surrogate-assisted MOEA/D	ParEGO [171], MOEA/D-EGO [172]	EGO
	MOEA/D-RBF [135], MOEA/D-RBF+LS [173], ELMOEA/D-DE [174], [175], K-CSEA [176]	Other models
	MOEA/D-S ³ [177], S-CMO [178]	
	EGO-MO [179], AB-MOEA [180], EPBII and EIPBII [181], TIC-SMEA [182], HSMEA [183]	New infill criterion
	SA-RVEA-PCA [184], K-RVEA(FS) [185]	Dimension reduction
	TEMO-MPS [186], MS-RV [187], GCS-MOE [188]	Transfer learning

TABLE A7
SELECTED WORKS FOR PREFERENCE INCORPORATION IN MOEA/D.

SUBCATEGORY	ALGORITHM NAME	CORE TECHNIQUE
A priori	MOEA/D-NUMS [189], R-MEAD [190], R-MEAD2 [191], IRMEAD [192]	Weight vector adaptation
	a-PICEA-g [193], cwMOEA/D [194]	Co-evolution
	MOEA/D-PRE [195]	Preference region
Interactive	PMA [196], iMOEA/D [197], PLVF [198], LTR [199], IEMO/D [200]	Progressive learning

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